

MODELING DRY FABRICS UNDER IMPACT WITH A 3D DISCRETE ELEMENT METHOD (DEM)

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ABSTRACT

Dry fabrics can be useful in aeronautic field to contain debris. Such structures are most of the time modeled with finite elements leading to heavy time calculations especially due to contact treatment. An alternative way to compute efficiently contact treatment in case of composite textile under dynamic impact is proposed in this work. An original 3D discrete element method is used for this purpose. It consists in a discrete representation of the fabrics at meso (yarn) and macro (textile) scales. The geometrical and mechanical modeling are first described taking into account a brittle elastic behavior for yarns and the frictional contact between them. Then basic concepts of the numerical method and the implementation of the model from a numerical point of view are presented. An impact simulation scenario is performed to validate the implementation satisfying the criterion of energy conservation. DEM are compared to finite elements ones but also to available experimental datas (work in progress).

1 INTRODUCTION

The weaving of high strength resistant yarns is commonly used in industrial applications as an impact energy absorber. Protective clothing, debris containment or textile-reinforced polymer are some examples of applications where dry fabrics made of stacking of 2D weaved plies (plain weaves or satin for instance) are largely encountered. This study is focused on impacts involving velocities higher than 60 m/s so that ballistic field could be addressed. Multiple plies of 2D weaving, as plain or satin, are used to create such absorbent structures. Only the ballistic impact regime is considered in this paper. It involves impact velocity higher than 80 m/s.

To simulate an impact on a dry fabrics and thus predict damages on the structure, two scales can be considered :

- the macromechanical approach consists in modeling the textile as a continuous media. A homogenized mechanical behaviour is adopted to simulate the fabrics deformation and failure using either the finite element method [1, 2] or an analytical solving [3, 4]. Discrete modeling approaches are also used in [5, 6, 7] by setting a mass-spring type system ;
- at the mesomechanical scale, each yarns of the textile is explicitly modeled and the complex contact effects between the yarns during the impact is dealt with. The finite element method provides strain and stress fields in [8, 9, 10, 11].

Both approaches tend to predict the dry fabric behavior and the projectile velocity. Comparison between these two techniques can be found in [12, 10]. It shows reasonable agreements between velocity measurements during an impact under fully fixed fabrics edges. Nevertheless, the complex friction effects between yarns and boundary conditions when two edges are fixed and the others free for a rectangular fabrics can not be properly described.

A mesomechanical approach is thus desirable to catch precisely local mechanisms mainly due to contact interaction between yarns. Using a standard finite element can lead to high CPU time when contacts are involved. While allowing a simple modeling of the yarns network including contacts, the present Discrete Element Methods [13] can be an efficient alternative to reduce time calculations. An original use of the Discrete Element Method for continuous media is developed in [14, 15] and is used in this work to model a yarn. The benefits of this approach is the natural consideration of contacts between elements in order to reduce time calculation.

2 MECHANICAL MODEL

2.1 Yarn behavior

For sake of simplicity, yarn is assumed to be a 2D-orthotropic material with a linear elastic behavior without strain rate dependencies. Shear and bending strains are assumed to be zero. The local frame is shown on Figure 1 with the 1-longitudinal direction and the 2-transverse one. Strain-stress relation is then reduced to, Eq. 1:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{11} \\ \varepsilon_{22} \\ \varepsilon_{12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{E_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{E_2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

with E_1 and E_2 , respectively denote the Young modulus in 1- and 2- direction.

The yarn failure criterion is based on the maximum strain ε_{max} . A brittle failure is assumed. No damage laws are included in the model.

Figure 1 : Framework for yarn modeling.

2.2 Contacts

Two contact interactions occurs during an impact on a dry fabrics. Contacts between the yarns and the impactor and contacts between yarns themselves. The friction force $\vec{F}_{friction}$ is supposed to be proportional to the normal contact force \vec{F}_n as, Eq. 2 :

$$\vec{F}_{friction} = \mu (\|\vec{v}_{slip}\|) \cdot \|\vec{F}_n\| \cdot \frac{\vec{v}_{slip}}{\|\vec{v}_{slip}\|} \quad (2)$$

The friction coefficient μ is based on a regularized Coulomb law. The regularization consists in using a function of the slipping velocity [Fig. 2]. Two friction coefficients are used. The first coefficient corresponds to the static friction μ_s which is greater than the second kinetic friction coefficient μ_k . The regularization function could be either a piecewise linear function or a decreasing exponential function below [11]. This last regularization is chosen and implemented in the present model. The friction function $\mu(\|\vec{v}_{slip}\|)$ becomes :

$$\mu(\|\vec{v}_{slip}\|) = \mu_k + (\mu_s - \mu_k) \cdot e^{-\alpha \|\vec{v}_{slip}\|} \quad (3)$$

Figure 2 : Regularization laws for Coulomb contact model.

3 DEM APPROACH

3.1 Basic concepts

Originally, the DEM permits to model granular medias taking into account the contact between the grains. For instance, it has been useful to treat the friction between two bodies involving a third body [16]. The method has been recently adapted [14] to model continuous media by using no-mass beams so that it could be used to deal with the continuous phase of the media before it becomes discontinuous when cracks occur. The present DEM is then able to manage cracks propagations inside the media with no extra numerical difficulties. Moreover, its ability to easily catch contacts between several parts tends the DEM to be a relevant method to simulate impacts on dry fabrics.

Inertia of the considered media is concentrated on the Discrete Elements (DE). The DE shape depends on the nature of the physical problem dealt with. In the present study, a spherical shape is retained.

The numerical solving consists in satisfying the dynamical equilibrium of each particles subjected to external and internal (coming from beams) forces using an explicit integration scheme [13].

The next section proposes a geometric representation of the yarn with spherical DE.

3.2 Geometric representation

Each yarn is modeled at mesoscopic scale. It is discretized with multiples DE, as it could be done the projectile with FE [11], and the fabrics (plain weave in this case) meshing results in a grid pattern, Figure 3. Same diameter and mass are adopted for each DE.

DE are uniformly distributed in the yarn section, supposed to be elliptic, figure 4. At this stage, improving the description of the elliptic section by adding DE is out of the scope. The DE density is simply determined by, Eq. 4 :

$$\rho_{DEM} = \rho_{macro} \frac{3 abL_{yarn}}{4 N_{yarn} R^3} , \quad (4)$$

with R , L_{yarn} , ρ_{macro} and N_{yarn} respectively denote the discrete element (DE) radius, the length of the yarn, the yarn density and the number of DEs in the yarn section. a and b are the semi-minor and semi-major axis of the ellipse.

Figure 3 : Comparison between a FEM geometry (a) [11] and a DEM geometry (b) for a plain weave

Figure 4 : Elliptic yarn section with DE.

3.2 Mechanical behavior in the DEM

3.2.1 Yarn stiffness

The simple 2D-orthotropic behavior of yarns is modeled with a pattern of longitudinal and transversal springs. Each spring are connected to two discrete elements [Fig. 5]. Two different stiffnesses are considered : K_1 for the longitudinal springs and K_2 for the transversal ones.

K_2 is assumed to be proportional to K_1 . The coefficient of proportionality c is fixed after sensitivity analysis. K_2 Allows to ensure the yarn cohesion in the transverse direction. It can be adjusted in case of longitudinal yarn preload.

K_1 Can be easily obtained from the E_1 Young modulus and K_2 deduced by proportionality, Eq. 5 :

$$K_1 = \frac{E_1 S}{N_2 2 R} , \quad (5)$$

$$K_2 = c K_1$$

where R and N_2 are respectively the radius of a spherical ED and the number of DE in the transverse direction.

Finally, each spring exerts two forces $\vec{F}_{s/1}$ and $\vec{F}_{s/2}$ respectively on the two discrete elements at its ends (noted 1 and 2) expressed as, Eq. 6 (a) :

$$(a) \quad \vec{F}_{s/1} = K_i \Delta L \vec{n} \quad \vec{F}_{s/2} = K_i \Delta L \vec{n} \quad (b) \quad \frac{\Delta L}{L_0} < \epsilon_{max} \quad (6)$$

where K_i is the corresponding longitudinal or transversal stiffness, ΔL the difference between the current length and the initial length L_0 of the spring and \vec{n} the normal vector of the support joining the centers of two adjacent DE. If the failure criterion is reached, Eq.5 (b), then the spring is removed from the calculation

Figure 5 : Spring pattern for a plain weave with DEM.

3.2.2 Contact management

The contact between DEs is naturally taken into account. When an interpenetration is detected (ie when the distance between two DE becomes lower than the sum of the radii of the two DE in contact), the reaction force \vec{F}_n between the two DE is computed as, Eq. 7 :

$$\vec{F}_n = \delta K_c \vec{n} , \quad (7)$$

where δ represents the interpenetration between two DEs and \vec{n} the unit normal support vector. The contact stiffness K_c is assumed to be the same that K_1 by numerical convenience and after sensitivity analysis.

The friction is taken into account by applying a tangential force \vec{F}_t using the friction coefficient μ and the previously computed normal contact force, Eq. 8 :

$$\vec{F}_t = \mu \|\vec{F}_n\| \cdot \frac{\vec{v}_{rel}}{\|\vec{v}_{rel}\|} , \quad (8)$$

where \vec{v}_{rel} is the relative velocity in the tangential plane between two DEs. It is obtained by a projection of the velocity difference in the tangential plane :

$$\vec{v}_{rel} = (\vec{v}_1 - \vec{v}_2) - \vec{n} \cdot (\vec{v}_1 - \vec{v}_2) \cdot \vec{n} . \quad (9)$$

4 IMPACT SIMULATION ON PLAIN WEAVE TEXTILE

As partially mentioned above, a preliminary sensitivity analysis was performed to answer the questions : i) the need or not to introduce an artificial numerical damping coefficient in the time scheme ii) the need or not to introduce a physical damping coefficient added via a Kelvin-Voigt model iii) what is the influence of the contact stiffness K_c value on the global behaviour ? On the stability of the numerical scheme ?

Results of the numerical campaign testing shows that no artificial damping coefficients are needed to obtain the solution convergence. The contact stiffness has no effect on the solution but requires a minimum value of $K_1/10$.

A 5 cm x 5 cm square plain weave ply of Kevlar fibers is considered with two clamped edges and two free edges. Three projectile velocities are addressed : 60 m/s, 90 m/s and 245 m/s. Only a quarter of the domain is modeled thanks to the double symmetry of the plain weaving. The projectile is a rigid sphere with a diameter of 5.35 mm impacting at the center of the fabric on the cross of two yarns. Datas needed for simulations are summed up in Table 1.

Yarn modulus E_1	[GPa]	62
Yarn section width	[mm]	0.59
Yarn section height	[mm]	0.115
Density	[kg/m ³]	1310
Woven thickness	[mm]	0.265
DE radius	[mm]	0.118

Table 1: Kevlar parameters.

4.1 Qualitative results

Figure 6 shows the damage progression during impact. A well-known pyramidal shape deformation is retrieved (Figure 7). The unweaving caused by the impact as well as the yarns failure under the projectile can be captured. The opposition of a yarn, initially not fixed at its ends, accompanying the projectile until it passes through the textile is remarkable, Figure 6(d).

Figure 6 : Displacement field for the impact at 245 m/s.

Figure 7 : Typical pyramidal shape during an impact.

CPU time for this calculation is between 7 hours for the 60 m/s velocity impact and 2.5 hours for the 245 m/s one. These times are greatly lower than in similar simulations using FEM [10] where CPU time are between 17 hours and 8 hours for the same impact velocities.

4.2 Energy analysis

This study was the opportunity to compute the energy balance during an impact. Thus, strain energy, contact energies (stiffness and friction) and kinetic energies (fabrics and projectile) can be assessed at each time of calculation. The energy balance during the impact at 245 m/s is plotted on Figure 8. The projectile kinetic energy decreases until the last yarn failure occurs (time~100 μs), then it remains constant. On the same time, a competition occurs between woven kinetic and strain energies. When a failure occurs in the fabric, the stored strain energy is released and transferred into kinetic energy. Friction effects during the impact induce a constant increasing energy. One can verify that the energy due to the artificial contact stiffness (named “contact energy” in figure 8) is insignificant compared to the others.

Finally, the conservation energy error during the simulation can be computed [Fig. 8(b)]. During the simulation, it never exceeds 0.7 %.

Figure 8 : Energy balance (a) and energy conservation error (b) during the impact at 245 m/s.

4.3 Projectile velocity

The evolution of the projectile velocity is plotted on Figure 9 for the three initial impactor velocities : 60 m/s, 90 m/s and 245 m/s. DEM results are compared with FEM [10] and one experimental measure.

For each velocity, DEM and FEM results are coincident at the beginning of impact; the 'decrimping' of the fabric is well described. In contrast, they don't match when the first yarn failures occur resulting in a change of slope. This change appears later with DEM. The slope becomes zero when the projectile is passed through the fabric; its velocity remains constant.

Results for 60 and 90 m/s are qualitatively in a good agreement with those found in [10]. A wider gap is observed for the higher impact velocity at 245 m/s. In this case, the predicted residual impactor velocity is 185 m/s whereas experimental result [17] and FEM prediction [10] respectively give 207 m/s and 225 m/s, figure 9. So, it is underestimated with DEM and overestimated with FEM.

Figure 9 : Projectile velocity for the three impacts simulation.

5 CONCLUSION AND PROSPECTS

Present results clearly show the capabilities of the DEM to deal with dry fabrics at mesoscopic scales. Qualitative results are mainly demonstrated in this paper but quantitative results are in progress and will be demonstrated at the conference.

Future impacts simulations will be performed on the interlock 3X weaving varying the number of DE and impact conditions to analyze the mass and velocity impactor but also the prestressed effects on global responses and failure progression in the textile. Then, coupling this DE model to a continuous one [10] is intended to be able to model larger woven target. Dry fabrics in hybrid structures (CFRP + Textile) for impact applications are also explored. Draping fabrics is another possible use of the method.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Shahkarami, A., & Vaziri, R. (2007). A continuum shell finite element model for impact simulation of woven fabrics. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, **34**(1), 104–119 (doi:[10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2006.06.010](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijimpeng.2006.06.010))
- [2] Lim, C. T., Shim, V. P. W., & Ng, Y. H. (2003). Finite-element modeling of the ballistic impact of fabric armor. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, **28**(1), 13–31. (doi:[10.1016/S0734-743X\(02\)00031-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0734-743X(02)00031-3))
- [3] Billon, H. H., & Robinson, D. J. (2001). Models for the ballistic impact of fabric armour. *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, **25**(4), 411–422. (doi:[10.1016/S0734-743X\(00\)00049-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0734-743X(00)00049-X))
- [4] Ha-Minh, C., Imad, A., Boussu, F., & Kanit, T. (2013). On analytical modelling to predict of the ballistic impact behaviour of textile multi-layer woven fabric. *Composite Structures*, **99**, 462–476. (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.10.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2012.10.011))
- [5] Ben Boubaker, B., Haussy, B., & Ganghoffer, J.-F. (2007). Discrete woven structure model: yarn-on-yarn friction. *Comptes Rendus Mécanique*, **335**(3), 150–158. (doi:[10.1016/j.crme.2007.02.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crme.2007.02.006))
- [6] Joo, K., & Jin Kang, T. (2007). Numerical Analysis of Multi-Ply Fabric Impacts. *Textile Research Journal*, **77**(6), 359–368. (doi:[10.1177/0040517507076746](https://doi.org/10.1177/0040517507076746))
- [7] Jauffrès, D., Sherwood, J. a., Morris, C. D., & Chen, J. (2009). Discrete mesoscopic modeling for the simulation of woven-fabric reinforcement forming. *International Journal of Material Forming*, **3**(S2), 1205–1216. (doi:[10.1007/s12289-009-0646-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12289-009-0646-y))
- [8] Duan, Y., Keefe, M., Bogetti, T. a., & Cheeseman, B. a. (2005). Modeling the role of friction during ballistic impact of a high-strength plain-weave fabric. *Composite Structures*, **68**(3), 331–337. (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2004.03.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2004.03.026))
- [9] Duan, Y., Keefe, M., Bogetti, T. a., & Powers, B. (2006). Finite element modeling of transverse impact on a ballistic fabric. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, **48**(1), 33–43. (doi:[10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2005.09.007](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2005.09.007))
- [10] Ha-Minh, C., Imad, A., Kanit, T., & Boussu, F. (2013). Numerical analysis of a ballistic impact on textile fabric. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences*, **69**, 32–39. (doi:[10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2013.01.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijmecsci.2013.01.014))
- [11] Rao, M. P., Duan, Y., Keefe, M., Powers, B. M., & Bogetti, T. a. (2009). Modeling the effects of yarn material properties and friction on the ballistic impact of a plain-weave fabric. *Composite Structures*, **89**(4), 556–566. (doi:[10.1016/j.compstruct.2008.11.012](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2008.11.012))

- [12] Grujicic, M., Bell, W. C., Arakere, G., He, T., Xie, X., & Cheeseman, B. a. (2009). Development of a Meso-Scale Material Model for Ballistic Fabric and Its Use in Flexible-Armor Protection Systems. *Journal of Materials Engineering and Performance*, **19**(1), 22–39. (doi:[10.1007/s11665-009-9419-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-009-9419-5))
- [13] André, D., Charles, J., Iordanoff, I., & Néauport, J. (2014). The GranOO workbench, a new tool for developing discrete element simulations, and its application to tribological problems. *Advances in Engineering Software*, **74**, 40–48. (doi:[10.1016/j.advengsoft.2014.04.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advengsoft.2014.04.003))
- [14] André, D., Iordanoff, I., Charles, J., & Néauport, J. (2012). Discrete element method to simulate continuous material by using the cohesive beam model. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 213-216, 113–125. (doi:[10.1016/j.cma.2011.12.002](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2011.12.002))
- [15] André, D., Jebahi, M., Iordanoff, I., Charles, J., & Néauport, J. (2013). Using the discrete element method to simulate brittle fracture in the indentation of a silica glass with a blunt indenter. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, **265**(8), 136–147. (doi:[10.1016/j.cma.2013.06.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cma.2013.06.008))
- [16] Iordanoff, I., Seve, B., & Berthier, Y. (2002). Solid Third Body Analysis Using a Discrete Approach: Influence of Adhesion and Particle Size on Macroscopic Properties. *Journal of Tribology*, **124**(3), 530. (doi:[10.1115/1.1456089](https://doi.org/10.1115/1.1456089))
- [17] Y Duan, M Keefe, ED Wetzel, TA Bogetti, B Powers, JE Kirkwood, and KM Kirkwood (2005). Effects of friction on the ballistic performance of a high-strength fabric structure. In *Impact Loading of Lightweight Structures.*, WITpress.